

Synthesis, characterization and redox behavior of nano-size $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$

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Abstract : Nanosized crystallites of the mixed oxides LaMnO_{3+x} (LM), $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{MnO}_{3-\gamma}$ (LSM) and $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSMF) were synthesized by alternative methods like nitrate route, drip pyrolysis and ceramic route followed by calcinations at different temperatures. The average crystallite size of LSMF was found to be 10, 25 and 90 nm respectively for the calcinations temperatures of 700, 1150 and 1400 °C. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies showed that the LSMF sample calcined at 900 °C had orthorhombic symmetry which transforms to rhombohedral phase above 1150 °C and this high temperature phase was found to be stable up to 1400 °C. Incorporation of iron into strontium-doped lanthanum manganite (LSM) was found to cause a structural rearrangement from rhombohedral to orthorhombic symmetry. The lattice parameters of these manganites were determined by indexing powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns. From Mössbauer spectrum it was confirmed that only one kind of iron is present in an asymmetric environment. Temperature programmed reduction (TPR) results indicated that (i) above systems contains Mn in +3 and +4 oxidation states, (ii) Fe reduces at lower temperature as compared to Mn^{4+} in rhombohedral LSMF and (iii) Fe^{3+} and Mn^{4+} undergo simultaneous reduction in orthorhombic LSMF phase.

Keywords : Nano technology solid state chemistry, redox behaviour

The physical properties of the rare earth manganites are known to be influenced by their defect structure, grain size, crystal structure etc.^{1,2}. Both pure and doped rare earth manganites exhibit high concentration of defects in the oxygen sub lattice. One rhombohedral and three orthorhombic crystal structures have been reported for the compound $\text{LaMnO}_{3\pm x}$ ³ and the structure of the rare earth manganites is found to be influenced by the overall Mn^{4+} content, La/Mn ratio and the temperature. In $\text{LaMnO}_{3\pm x}$ and $(\text{La}, \text{Sr})\text{MnO}_{3\pm \gamma}$, the Mn^{4+} content and γ (or x) are interrelated and is a measure of the nonstoichiometry. Lanthanum strontium ferromanganites $(\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x)(\text{Mn}_{1-\gamma}\text{Fe}_\gamma)\text{O}_{3\pm \delta}$ crystallize in either cubic or rhombohedral symmetry⁴ and in a specific case of $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3\pm \delta}$, a transition from rhombohedral to cubic occurred in going from the full to low oxygenated state. Such structural changes in these nonstoichiometric compounds are associated with defect formation influencing their electrical and magnetic properties⁵, thermal expansion behavior⁶, sintering characteristics⁷ and catalytic properties^{8,9}. Isupova *et al.* have shown¹⁰ that $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$ had a high degree of mis-orientation of microblock causing the highest activity in the series $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{O}_3$ for CO catalytic oxidation. During our recent investigations¹¹ on the electrical and thermo-mechanical properties of $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$, we found that Fe doping of LM or LSM had consid-

erable influence on their crystal structure. The particle size of these samples was found to be influenced by the method of sample preparation¹¹. This prompted us to investigate the effects of preparative method, crystal structure and grain size on the redox behavior of $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$.

In the present investigation we have used low temperature nitrate route, drip pyrolysis and high temperature ceramic route to synthesize nano-sized perovskite oxides $\text{LaMnO}_{3\pm x}$ (LM), $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{MnO}_{3\pm \gamma}$ (LSM) and $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSMF) samples, with an objective to compare their particle size, surface area, crystal structure and redox behavior.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the results of particle size and surface area measurements and also the crystal symmetry of $\text{LaMnO}_{3\pm x}$, $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{MnO}_{3\pm \gamma}$ and $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ samples synthesized by different routes. LSM showed higher crystallite size of ~30 nm as compared to Fe-substituted LSM samples having 15–18 nm particle size. As compared to LSMF prepared by drip pyrolysis, the nitrate route samples were found to have lower particle size and a higher surface area (Table 1). In drip pyrolysis, nitrate droplets were suddenly brought to 700 °C and then the sample was

Table 1. Effect of different synthesis route on particle size, surface area and symmetry

Sample	Synthesis route								
	Drip pyrolysis (900 °C)			Nitrate route (900 °C)			Ceramic route (1100 °C)		
	SA (m ² g ⁻¹)	PS (nm)	Sym	SA (m ² g ⁻¹)	PS (nm)	Sym	SA (m ² g ⁻¹)	PS (nm)	Sym
LM	-	-	Rhom.	-	31-34	Rhom	-	43-46	Rhom
LSM	-	30-33	Rhom	3.8	26-28	Rhom	-	49-51	Rhom
LSMF	1.99	20-22	Ortho	7	15-17	Ortho	1.0	46-50	Rhom

SA = surface area, PS = particle size, Sym. = symmetry

LM = LaMnO_{3±x}, LSM = La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}MnO_{3±y}

LSMF = La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}O_{3-δ}

heated further to 900 °C. On the other hand, slow evaporation occurred at 80 °C in the case of nitrate route and the solidus pulp was subjected to further heating at 900 °C. This may be the cause of their lower particle size as well as higher surface area.

La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}O_{3-δ} sample was calcined at different temperatures for 24 h and it was observed that the crystallite sizes varied from 9 to 11 nm at 700 °C, 15-17 nm of 900 °C (7.0), 31-38 at 1100 °C (2.1) and 78-95 at 1400 °C (surface area).

The XRD patterns of freshly synthesized LaMnO_{3±x}, La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}MnO_{3±y} and La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}O_{3-δ} are shown in Fig. 1. The XRD patterns of LaMnO_{3±x} (Fig. 1a) and La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}MnO_{3±y} (Fig. 1b) samples calcined at 900 °C were found to be identical and matched with the rhombohedral structure of LaMnO_{3.15} (PCPDF 32-0484). This phase was found to be stable up to 1400 °C. Along with this rhombohedral phase, XRD lines due to La₂O₃ were also noticed (Fig. 1a). The iron doped samples (La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}O_{3-δ})

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of LM, LSM and LSMF synthesized by nitrate route

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of LSMF calcined at different temperatures calcined at 900 °C indicated a different XRD pattern (Fig. 1c). But the same sample when heated at 1100 °C produced a XRD pattern (Fig. 1d) which was similar to the rhombohedral phase of LaMnO_{3±x}. It is more clearly demonstrated in Fig. 2, which depicts variation in 100% peak of La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}O_{3-δ} as a function of calcination temperature. Both the XRD patterns were indexed and cell parameters of La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Mn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}O_{3-δ} were generated using powder pattern indexing program. Parameters are : 900 °C (ortho) *a* (Å) 5.4465, *b* (Å) 5.5173, *c* (Å) 7.7598, *V* (Å³) 2.3306; 1100 °C (rhombo) *a* (Å) 5.5294, *c* (Å) 13.3721, *V* (Å³) 354.04. Low temperature LSMF material could be indexed for orthorhombic symmetry and the high temperature phase could be indexed with rhombohedral symmetry. Thus splitting in *d*₂₀₀ peak (*I*/*I*₀ = 100%) with increase in calcination temperature marks the phase transformation from orthorhombic to rhombohedral above 1100 °C. Lines due to La₂O₃ are not observed in LSMF samples. In a recent investigation on lanthanum-strontium ferromanganites, (La_{1-x}Sr_x)(Mn_{1-y}Fe_y)O_{3±δ} samples with *x* and *y* = 0.2, 0.5 and 0.7

heated to 1300 °C were reported to be crystallizing in rhombohedral symmetry⁴. Thus the orthorhombic phase could be stabilized by doping Fe in LSM and by synthesizing at a lower temperature (i.e. below 900 °C).

Fig. 3 XRD patterns of LSMF as a function of different synthetic routes (900 °C) (a) nitrate solution, (b) drip pyrolysis, (c) solid state, *La₂O₃ phase

The XRD patterns of LSMF obtained by various synthetic routes and heated at 900 °C are shown in Fig. 3. XRD patterns of sample prepared by drip pyrolysis and nitrate route were identical (Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b). But when it was prepared by solid-state route, at 900 °C reaction was found to be incomplete which can be seen in Fig. 3c. Hence these samples were further calcined at 1100 °C for 48 h to obtain pure LSMF phase. This reveals that LSMF when prepared by ceramic route (calcined at 1100 °C) shows rhombohedral structure with a lattice parameter $a_0 = 5.5294 \text{ \AA}$ and $c_0 = 13.3721 \text{ \AA}$. On the other hand, the sample prepared by nitrate route (calcined at 900 °C) shows orthorhombic structure with a lattice parameters $a_0 = 5.4465 \text{ \AA}$, $b_0 = 5.5143 \text{ \AA}$ and $c_0 = 7.7598 \text{ \AA}$. Thus, solution based techniques of material synthesis give homogeneous products. Moreover, phases that cannot be stabilized to room temperature by solid-state synthesis can be achieved by adopting the solution route. The crystallite size and shape of LSMF can be further noted from the photograph of transmission electron microscopy (Fig. 4). A TEM image of these perovskite samples reveals that they consist of rather larger size particles with typical dimensions greater than 1 μm , composed of microblocks or clusters.

In order to identify the site(s), occupied by the substituted iron atoms, their valence state(s), the evaluation of valence state(s) (if any) and to understand local effects of

Fig. 4. TEM photographs of LSMF

the substitution, the technique of Mossbauer spectroscopy was employed. A room temperature Mossbauer spectrum of LSMF is shown in Fig. 5. The isomer shift values reflect the presence of Fe in +3 state only. Absence of any signatures of Fe in +2, +4 and +5 state in the spectra further indicates non-participation of Fe in the charge disproportionation. The most favorable site for iron to occupy in this matrix is that of Mn because of their comparable ionic radii and characteristic d-shell chemistry that stabilizes perovskite configuration via typically MO₆ octahedra.

Fig. 5. Mossbauer spectra of LSMF

Mossbauer spectrum at ambient temperature of LSMF (Fig. 5) could be fitted with one symmetric doublet. This indicates that only one type of Fe is present which is in an asymmetric environment. Similar phenomenon of paramagnetic component was reported on Ca, Sr and Ba substituted magnetic materials and interpreted as the formation of paramagnetic clusters¹³⁻¹⁶. It indicates that paramagnetic component may be due to cluster formation.

Fig. 6. TPR curves of LSMF synthesized at two different temperatures

Redox behavior :

The reduction profiles (TPR) of LSMF synthesized at two different temperatures is shown in Fig. 6. In case of 900 °C synthesized orthorhombic phase Mn and Fe reduces simultaneously. But in case of rhombohedral phase obtained at 1100 °C, multiple bands were seen with an additional band at lower temperature (~350 °C). Thus we conclude that in orthorhombic LSMF, Fe and Mn are evenly distributed. But in case of rhombohedral phase Fe and Mn occupy specific positions.

TPR profiles of rhombohedral LSM and LSMF are shown in Fig. 7. In LSM only Mn is a reducible species whereas in case of LSMF, Mn as well as Fe can be reduced. TPR profile of LSM shows that Mn starts reducing at ~350 °C and is completed at 1000 °C (Fig. 7a). This profile clearly indicates that reduction of manganese takes place in three steps having T_{max} at 520, 720 and 900 °C with overlapping 2nd and 3rd steps. One type of Mn reduces between 350–600 °C and other two types are reduced at higher temperature. Buciuman *et al.*¹⁷ have carried out TPR study of $La_{0.8}A'_{0.2}MnO_{3+\delta}$ ($A' = Sr, Ba, K, Cs$) along with $LaMnO_3$. They have shown that in rhombohedral $LaMnO_3$, Mn is present as +4 as well as in +3 states and that Mn^{4+} starts reducing at lower temperature as compared to Mn^{3+} . The XRD pattern of the TPR residue of LSM showed the presence of La_2O_3 , MnO and $SrMn_3O_{6-\delta}$ (Fig. 8).

The reduction of strontium substituted lanthanum manganites is likely to follow the scheme :

Fig. 7. TPR profiles of LSM and Fe doped LSM samples

Buciuman *et al.*¹⁷ had concluded from their redox studies on similar perovskites that on partial substitution of La^{3+} by Sr^{2+} the charge is compensated by lowering the oxidative nonstoichiometry, while keeping the tetravalent man-

Fig. 8. XRD pattern of (a) LSMF, (b) after TPO and (c) after TPR

ganese practically unchanged. It was further supported by wet chemical analysis reported by Anderson *et al.*¹⁸. Thus we conclude that the low temperature reduction is due to $Mn^{4+} \rightarrow Mn^{3+}$ and at high temperature one, i.e. above 600 °C, is due to Mn^{3+} to Mn^{2+} .

In rhombohedral LSMF where part of Mn is substituted by Fe, an additional TPR band develops with T_{max} at ~350 °C and the bands at higher temperature is greatly reduced (Fig. 7b). Thus the shift of TPR profile to lower temperature is actually due to iron getting reduced at lower temperature as compared to manganese. The reduction in size of bands at higher temperatures is due to Mn^{3+} which is substituted by Fe^{3+} . In case of 2nd TPR cycle of LSMF where TPO run was carried out between 1st and 2nd cycle, it was observed that reduction profile has shifted to lower temperature with $T_{max} \sim 350$ °C. This is because between two TPR runs TPO run was carried out where sample is heated in oxygen atmosphere, so part of Mn^{3+} might get converted to Mn^{4+} and that starts reducing at lower temperature. The subsequent TPR cycles were identical to 2nd TPR cycle. The XRD patterns of the residue of LSMF after TPR and TPO are shown in Fig. 8. The XRD pattern of the TPR residue of LSMF (Fig. 8c) shows lines due to La_2O_3 , MnO , $SrMn_3O_{6-x}$ and $Sr_4Fe_3O_{9-y}$ indicating that when LSMF is heated in 5% H_2 atmosphere it decomposes and during cooling Fe^{2+} converts to Fe^{3+} to give $Sr_4Fe_3O_{9-y}$. On re-oxidation i.e. after TPO cycle (Fig. 8b), the various component of TPR residue combines to give LSMF as major phase with $SrFeLaO_4$ and $SrFe_2O_4$ and as an impurity phases.

Conclusions :

Fe substitution in LSM (26–28 nm) is found to result in considerably reduced particle size (15–18 nm) and a higher surface area as compared to LSM. LSMF shows orthorhombic system at 900 °C and stabilizes in rhombohedral phase of LSM at higher temperature. Orthorhombic LSMF could be synthesized by nitrate route, drip pyrolysis and not by solid-state route. In orthorhombic LSMF, Fe^{3+} and Mn^{4+} reduces simultaneously whereas in rhombohedral LSMF, Fe reduces at a lower temperature as compared to Mn.

Experimental

1 M nitrate solutions of Sr, Fe and Mn were prepared by dissolving $SrCO_3$, Fe-metal and $MnCO_3$ in nitric acid and for La, $La(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ was used directly. Nitrate solutions of the various cations are mixed together in the appropriate ratios and the solutions were used to prepare different compositions by various routes like nitrate method and drip pyrolysis. In nitrate route, the mixed nitrate solutions were

dried at 80 °C and the resulting solidus pulp was calcined at different temperatures namely, 600, 900, 1100 and 1400 °C. In drip pyrolysis, the droplets of mixed nitrate solution were directly subjected to 750 °C and the resultant product was collected. In the case of standard ceramic route, $SrCO_3$ along with oxides of La, Fe and Mn were used as starting materials. Freshly heated (~900 °C) lanthanum sesquioxide was used to avoid formation of oxycarbonate and hydroxides of La. All the samples were stable in oxygen as well as in helium atmosphere up to temperature of 900 °C.

Powder XRD patterns of all the samples were recorded on a Philips X-ray Diffractometer (PW 1710) with Ni filtered CuK_{α} radiation, using silicon as an external standard. The patterns were indexed to generate their lattice dimensions using powder program¹². From XRD line broadening, particle size measurements were carried out using Scherrer equation. Surface areas were measured by N_2 sorption using BET equation on Quantchrome Instruments (model Autosorb). ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectra were obtained at room temperature in a constant acceleration mode. The samples were mixed with diluting agent, i.e. Li_2CO_3 and iron content was maintained constant at 0.2 mg cm^{-2} of ^{57}Fe in all the absorbers. The spectrophotometer was calibrated with α -Fe and the isomer shift values are given relative to this. The experimental data were fitted by a least square curve fitting program using the sum of spectral components characterizing different iron phases.

The grain sizes of different samples were measured using transmission electron microscopy, with the help of a Jeol 2000 FX TEM instrument operating at 120 kV. The samples were prepared by ultrasonating the finely ground samples in ethanol and then dispersing on a carbon film supported on a copper grid. Electron micrographs presented in this study are bright field images. The enlarged size prints of TEM micrographs were used to arrive at a reasonably precise particle size distribution data.

For evaluating redox behavior as a function of sample composition. TPR profiles were recorded with a TPDRO-1100 analyzer (Thermoquest, Italy), using H_2 (5%) + Ar gas mixture as a reduction medium. All the samples were pre-treated by heating in an inert atmosphere at 600 °C for one hour prior to recording of the first TPR run. A soda lime trap was connected before TCD detector to absorb any moisture formed. The experiments were carried out in range 27–900 °C at a heating rate of 6° per minute. Successive 5–6 runs of TPR/TPO were recorded on each sample so as to examine the stability of these compositions over such redox cycles.

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